

Report on the outcomes of a Virtual Mobility¹

Action number:

Grantee name: Jana Preissler

Virtual Mobility Details

Title: Testing of DL_toolbox for Vaisala WindCube Scan lidars

Start and end date: 09/02/2023 to 15/02/2023

Description of the work carried out during the VM

Description of the virtual collaboration and activities carried out during the VM, with focus on the work carried out by the grantee. Any deviations from the initial working plan shall also be described in this section.

(max. 500 words)

The DL_toolbox, for standardised processing of Doppler wind lidar data, was tested on seven WindCube Scan lidars from four different institutes, spanning different time periods. The focus of testing was on established applications, namely the wind reconstruction from Doppler beam swinging (DBS) and velocity azimuth display (VAD) scan types, but also fixed stare (FIXED) and principal plane indicator (PPI) scan processing were tested.

We used a github repository (https://github.com/mkay-atm/dl_toolbox) to update the code. The github platform was also used to report and discuss issues. In addition, there were few virtual meetings between MK and JP to further discuss problems with the code and its application. Intermediate feedback was given to the other participants and data owners, who will also receive a copy of this report. A concluding meeting with all participants shall be scheduled.

We found the following issues, and implemented changes accordingly.

Issue	Fix
Wind reconstruction from full PPI was not implemented.	PPI scans of the full circle are now processed, with a complete set of output.

¹ This report is submitted by the grantee to the Action MC for approval and for claiming payment of the awarded grant. The Grant Awarding Coordinator coordinates the evaluation of this report on behalf of the Action MC and instructs the GH for payment of the Grant.

Colour scale minimum and maximum of backscatter plot was set to minimum and maximum of data range. As the backscatter plot is on a logarithmic scale, features became invisible.	Backscatter colour scale was set to a fixed range, improving visibility of boundary layer and other aerosol features. Besides, plotting speed was improved.
Colour scale minimum and maximum of horizontal wind speed plot was set to minimum and maximum of data range. In case of single high-wind-speed outliers, other wind features became invisible.	Horizontal wind speed colour scale was set dynamically from 0 m/s to the 95 th percentile of the displayed wind data, making all wind features within the boundary layer well visible.
Naming of variables in netcdf files differ between versions of WindCube Scan and for different scan types. For example: "elevation", "ele", "zenith" are used for elevation and zenith angles. When reading netcdf file of FIXED scan type, "elevation" variable could not be found.	Variables are read depending on scan type.
In newer data file versions, variables are found in different locations than in data files of older WindCube Scan lidars. In our example, "time_reference" could not be found.	The code was changed to find the variable "time_reference" in older and newer files.
Backscatter plots of VAD were not available due to a problem in identifying sweep cycles.	Sweep cycle identification condition was corrected.
Corrupt input files led to complete stop of processing.	Corrupt files are now skipped when reading the data. Processing continues with remaining data.

The table below shows a summary of testing success rate after the changes above were implemented. The processing of full circle PPI scans has been newly setup in the framework of this VM.

Scan type	Number of tested instruments	Output: LVL1 netcdf	Output: LVL2 netcdf	Output: Backscatter quicklook	Output: Wind quicklook
DBS	6	100%	100%	100%	100%
VAD	1	100%	100%	100%	100%
PPI (full circle)	2	100%	100%	100%	100%
PPI (sector)	1	100%	n/a	n/a	n/a
FIXED	6	100%	n/a	100%	n/a

Description of the VM main achievements and planned follow-up activities

Description and assessment of whether the VM achieved its planned goals and expected outcomes, including specific contribution to Action objective and deliverables, or publications resulting from the VM. Agreed plans for future follow-up collaborations shall also be described in this section.

(max. 500 words)

The work carried out in the framework of this VM extended the capabilities of the DL_toolbox by one more scan type. Besides, the toolbox is now better able to process different scan strategies, and a variety of input files from Vaisala WindCube Scan lidars of widely different manufacturing date. External testing of the toolbox also highlighted some required changes of the documentation. We recommend updating the installation guide, add a note on the expected input data folder structure, create a more compact configuration file, and add information on the use in general, for example on data availability and averaging.

While this project focussed on testing the functionality of DL_toolbox, further tests on the wind reconstruction itself are recommended. This includes data quality screening parameters, retrieval thresholds, and averaging. We also recommend further testing of the output, for example of different scan types that are repeated in succession, as well as comparison of the retrieved wind data to independent sensors. This was investigated by the code developers before for other kinds of Doppler lidars. We expect equally high quality of wind reconstruction for WindCube Scan lidars.

As shown in the table above, VAD scans could only be tested from one station. More VAD testing is therefore recommended, especially testing of data quality screening parameters.

Lastly, we recommend including the real-time data format of the Vaisala WindCube Profiler in the toolbox. The instrument provides DBS data similar to that of the WindCube Scan DBS. However, the data is stored in csv files. Therefore, setting up a read-in routine for the WindCube Profiler data files should suffice to unlock a much larger number of continuously running instruments, for example for E-Profile.

In the view towards E-Profile we could show the flexibility of DL_toolbox to handle a variety of scan types and WindCube Scan file versions. Provided a high quality of wind reconstruction, we can recommend DL_toolbox as an excellent toolbox for standardised processing of Doppler wind data in the framework of E-Profile.

This VM also paves the way for a PROBE summer school, that will be organised by MeteoSwiss. The objective will be training a broad community in using DL_toolbox. Further details will be available shortly.